

TO ZERO AND BEYOND

Zero Energy Residential Buildings Study

2017 Inventory of residential projects on the
path to zero in the U.S. and Canada

APRIL 2018

INTRODUCTION

We're going exponential!

Zero (net) energy (ZE, ZNE) – building something that produces enough energy onsite to meet its own needs on an annual basis – is a “sticky” idea. People grasp it, and they like it; it’s captivating and motivating. What’s the power of ZE? It evokes self-sufficiency, and for many, fairness – taking no more than their share of resources. It’s also a specific, concrete goal, not an abstraction like “green” or “energy-efficient” (as compared to what?). And it’s a major accomplishment, a satisfying outcome for one’s efforts.

This year’s inventory bears out the allure of ZE, showing a growth rate in 2017 more than double that of 2016 – last year saw a 70% increase in ZE housing units, versus a 33% increase in 2016 over our baseline 2015 inventory.

This is exciting news, but it’s just a harbinger of some larger trends:

- Cities and other public agencies, including school districts, are on the forefront of ZE developments, as ZE buildings – both new and existing – emerge as principal emissions reduction targets in local climate action plans.
- More production home builders and multifamily developers are joining the ZE flock, heralding a sea change in the production housing market.
- Electrification (a.k.a. decarbonization) is a theme resonating within the ZE community worldwide. The message is inescapable: natural gas is on its way out as a fuel of choice.
- Awareness is growing that achieving ZNE on an annual basis overlooks the larger need to achieve a balance between production and consumption hour to hour, day to day, season to season — this is a significant current focus for progressive state governments, grid operators, and utilities.
- Embodied carbon in buildings is gaining traction as a key concern as word gets out that the carbon emissions associated with materials extraction, product manufacturing, and construction represent between 40 and 80 percent of a building’s total emissions over its first 20 years ... and these are the 20 years of greatest concern relative to throttling back the engine of climate change¹. This has many implications, including the imperative to rehabilitate and refurbish existing buildings in preference to building new ones.
- ZE buildings are increasingly recognized as just one in a suite of strategies for communities to tackle their zero carbon (ZC) goals. ZC community designs are incorporating local clean energy production at a variety of scales, from residential rooftop solar arrays to warehouses and parking

garages with production capacity serving much more than their own loads, along with storage for load balancing on the grid, and community microgrids to serve localized critical needs during power outages.

Resiliency is perhaps the most powerful driver behind many of these trends, as the increasing tempo and severity of climate-induced calamities make it ever more apparent that we need change, and we need it now.

The Net Zero Energy Coalition salutes the building pioneers, advocates, and policy makers who are fueling this necessary change, and whose impressive achievements are reflected in these pages. You are all heroes.

FINDINGS

Last year we said, “We love to be surprised – 33% growth in a single year” and, “we fully anticipate explosive growth in coming years.” This year we can say, “We love being right!” Seeing the number of ZE units more than double the rate of growth in a single year (from 33% in 2016 to 70% in 2017) is both gratifying and validating – ZE is on an exponential growth trajectory.

US annualized housing starts totaled 1.24 million as of February 2018; housing starts over the same period in Canada totaled 229,700. As our inventory numbers represent projects in multiple stages (in design, under construction, and completed – see page 9), we can’t accurately provide an estimate of the fraction of construction activity that ZE represents; however, it is safe to say that we have a long way to go, as ZE homes still represent a very tiny fraction of all new residential construction activity.

Some other macro findings this year include:

- Echoing the growth in units, the pace of growth as measured by number of buildings increased more than twofold, from 22% in 2016 to 49% in 2017; Growth in the number of projects diminished as compared with 2016 (56% versus 82% last year); but also
- We found a greater increase in the number of units (70%) than in the number of projects (56%);
- Taken together, these indicate an overall increase in project size;
- ZE development in Canada (see page 4) skews even more heavily to multifamily than in the US, with 77% of its ZE units in multifamily projects, versus 58% in the US.

Note: Although “zero energy” suggests precision, the inventory sought to identify all residential ZE projects designed to achieve energy performance in the realm of zero. All projects designed with this aim importantly contribute to creating a clean energy future, and to our understanding of the market for ZE development in the US and Canada. It is also important to note that the inventory relies on individuals to report their projects’ performance based on their best understanding of our definitions (page 10); NZEC does not verify performance.

PATH TO ZERO IN THE U.S. AND CANADA

- 5,000+ Units
- 1,000–4,999 Units
- 100–999 Units
- 10–99 Units
- 0–9 Units

1. Sacramento, CA	853
2. Vancouver, BC	723
3. Davis, CA	664
4. Portland, OR	365
5. New York, NY	361
6. Austin, TX	346
7. Honolulu, HI	338
8. Clarkdale, AZ	323
9. Washington DC	317
10. National City	268
11. Calgary, AB	210
12. Chino Valley, AZ	209
13. Townsend, MD	198
14. Carlsbad, CA	170
15. Boston, MA	165
16. San Ysidro, CA	160
17. Rotterdam, NY	160
18. Port St. Lucie, FL	154
19. Los Angeles, CA	153
20. Washtenaw, MI	150

	MULTI-FAMILY UNITS	SINGLE-FAMILY UNITS	TOTAL UNITS
Canada	1,089	327	1,416
USA	7,234	5,256	12,490
TOTAL	8,323	5,583	13,906

ZERO ENERGY DEVELOPMENT IS A VIABLE BUSINESS OPPORTUNITY

The 2017 inventory solidifies a key finding from both prior inventories: projects of two or more units (both single- and multifamily) dominate ZE activity across the US and Canada; they represented 94% of all ZE units in 2015, 95% in 2016, and once again totaled 94% in 2017.

This remarkable consistency is a clear signal that ZE residential development is not a custom building niche; it is a viable – and thriving – commercial construction activity, albeit still a small fraction of the market.

Of these projects (comprising 2+ units), 64% are in multifamily buildings, with an average project size of 47 units; the remaining 36% are in single-family developments, with an average project size of 38 units.

Further, multifamily projects are maintaining their overall prevalence over single-family activity, showing a small gain this year to reach 60% of all ZE units in 2017 as compared with 58% in 2016.

California’s Capital region continues to hold title to both the largest multifamily and the largest single-family ZE project:

- Multifamily – University of California Davis West Village (663 units, completed and occupied; reported as zero energy ready)
- Single-family – Ranch Capital LLC’s Northwest Land Park (800 units, in design; reported as zero energy ready)

A number of geographic patterns can also be observed from the map on page 4:

- California remains the volume ZE leader, with Arizona in second place, firmly anchoring the center of gravity for ZE residential activity in the southwest corner of the US
- Other strong regions include the Pacific Northwest and western Canada, the remainder of the US Southwest, a belt stretching across the Northeast and Great Lakes region, Hawaii, and Florida
- The Heartland, Alaska, and Canadian far north remain the areas of least ZE residential activity

As in the past, many of the city and state/province rankings (pages 4 and 7, respectively) can be directly attributed to large ZE projects.

PROJECTS COMPRISING 2+ UNITS

SINGLE-FAMILY VS. MULTIFAMILY UNITS

ZE BUILDER VOICES

ZE builders share key lessons they've learned on their personal paths to zero. Many emphasize that they're not just selling lower utility bills or carbon emissions; they're selling homes that offer improved comfort, resiliency, and air quality – indoors and out.

BRANDON DEYOUNG, DEYOUNG PROPERTIES, CA

On messaging: *Zero energy is a complicated issue and we try to simplify as much as possible. We don't say "net," just call it a "zero energy home." Subhead after "zero energy home" is "a home that is designed with the potential to produce as much energy as it uses in a year." Back up the information in the head with fine print.*

On electrification: *In our EnVision homes, the only gas will be for cooking; we have an induction option and some are upgrading to that. Some plans have a gas fireplace, but many buyers delete that. Gas is plumbed to the clothes dryer location, but most buyers end up choosing electric. It's just a matter of time and consumer education to get to all-electric homes.*

ANTHONY AEBI, GREENHILL CONTRACTING, NY

On keeping it simple: *Our homes are simpler. This keeps costs down and improves thermal performance. We use 100% standard designs including solar, no combustion appliances, 100% electric. Our spectrum of buyers all realize that paying a bit more up front will save them in the long run.*

GENE MYERS, THRIVE HOME BUILDERS, CO

On speaking to the heart: *We have learned to adopt a less-is-more approach. The best example is how we sell health in the home — we show a girl in a high chair with her mom feeding her. The caption is, "The air she breathes is just as important as the food she eats." This resonates with buyers and their values.*

On making ZE accessible: *Modern consumers want to buy what we build. They want to exercise their conscience if it doesn't cost them too much more, so cost is what we need to address. In my view, there are no other barriers. What we've really done is figure out how to make it as cost-effective as possible. I ask prospective buyers, "If you give me \$100 a month, I'll save you \$300 a month [HERS report estimate]; over the life of the home, that amounts to a big pile of money. How does that feel, saving money from Day 1?"*

JOSH SALINGER, BIRDSMOUTH CONSTRUCTION, OR

On delivering value: *More and more people are expressing knowledge and awareness of ZNE. We are getting more inquiries now that mention energy efficiency and zero energy right at the outset. What separates us from other builders in our market is that we're offering these features – comfort, performance, and quality – at close to cost parity with conventional homes.*

GEORGE KOERTZEN, HABITAT FOR HUMANITY OF SAN JOAQUIN COUNTY, CA

On achieving ZNE at low cost: *We've found ways to build to ZNE without spending extra money. Although some features, like added insulation, do cost more, others cost less. For example, we build homes with a framing factor of 0.13 — that means we're using half of the framing lumber of a typical home. Not only do we save on lumber, it's also less to haul, nail, and cut, saving on labor and waste. Same thing for the mechanical systems: with compact system design, we've reduced piping and ducting. Because of the added insulation and airtightness of our building shell, we can use a ¾-ton heat pump for a 1200 sf home — instead of the typical 2.5- or 3-ton unit. We're actually saving money by building this way.*

TOP ZERO ENERGY BUILDERS & DEVELOPERS

BUILDERS/DEVELOPERS WITH 10+ PROJECTS

BrightBuilt Home	79
Greenhill Contracting Inc.	36
Palo Duro Homes, Inc	20
Clifton View Homes	19
Latitude 38 LLC	15
Mandalay Homes Inc.	14
BPC Green Builders, Inc	14
Cooperation For Better Housing	14
Charles Thomas Homes	12
Decker Homes, Inc	10
Green Hammer	10

TOP 10 BUILDERS/DEVELOPERS BY NUMBER OF UNITS

Mandalay Homes Inc.	903
Ranch Capital LLC	800
Cooperation For Better Housing	697
Carmel Partners - UC Davis	662
Recollective	358
Planet Greenenergy	351
Tesha Malama	338
Community Housing Works	302
Landmark Homes	221
Affirmed Housing	296

TOP 10 ZERO ENERGY STATES/PROVINCES BY NUMBER OF UNITS

STATE	UNITS
CA	5,279
AZ	1,021
BC	829
NY	815
MA	523
TX	431
OR	421
MT	403
FL	372
PA	360
HI	357
WA	282
All Others	2,813

THESE STATES AND PROVINCES ARE NEW TO THE TOP 10:	
	AZ
	BC
	MT
	PA

THESE STATES AND PROVINCES ARE NO LONGER AMONG THE TOP 10:	
	HI
	DC
	NM
	AB

ENERGY PERFORMANCE

PERCENTAGE OF UNITS BY ENERGY PERFORMANCE

Note: In the 2015 and 2016 inventories, we called out Thousand Home Challenge (THC) projects – deep energy reductions in existing homes, achieved by a combination of structural and behavioral changes – as a distinct category. However, THC projects exist on the full spectrum of energy performance included in the inventory – zero energy ready, zero energy, and net positive – so we have updated our reporting to reflect those different performance levels. Accordingly, the THC projects are no longer shown separately but are instead distributed among the performance categories. We continue to differentiate THC and other projects in our inventory by asking data providers to indicate participation in various programs. We also collect data on projects that are new construction, retrofits, and/or a combination of both.

IN THE PIPELINE

The numbers cited earlier in this report represent only those projects that have moved past the earliest, most uncertain phase of the development life cycle — they are in design, under construction, or completed. Many, many more projects — representing more than 33,000 housing units — have been reported in the earlier, planning, stages. As in prior years' inventories, just a few planned projects make up the majority of that total:

- 21,500 units in Santa Clarita, CA
Newhall Ranch, by FivePoint
- 5,000 units in Waterset, FL
EcoVillage Waterset, by Planet Greenergy
- 2,900 units in Prescott Valley, AZ
Jasper, by Mandalay Homes
- 1,900 units in London, ON
West 5, Phase 2, by Sifton Properties

RESIDENTIAL ZERO ENERGY PIPELINE

COMPLETED

8,547
UNITS

956
PROJECTS

UNDER CONSTRUCTION

2,940
UNITS

126
PROJECTS

IN DESIGN

2,419
UNITS

72
PROJECTS

PLANNED

33,324
UNITS

44
PROJECTS

BACKGROUND

ZERO ENERGY BASICS

In simplest terms, a zero net energy building is one that produces as much renewable energy as it consumes each year — the “net” referring to the annual balance between energy production and energy consumption. In non-technical contexts, many practitioners are migrating to the more conversational term, “zero energy.”

The most common renewable energy source for a zero-energy home is a photovoltaic (PV) array, typically roof-mounted but occasionally freestanding on the building site.

However, zero net energy is achieved by working on energy reduction, as well as on energy production. Thus a high degree of energy efficiency is at the core of zero-energy projects; without that foundation, few projects would have space for a PV array large enough to meet their annual energy needs.

PROJECT CATEGORIES

“Zero,” in theory, is an absolute, yet the reality is that many homes, although they may not achieve that absolute goal, are designed as part of the larger movement towards zero energy, and we can learn from all of them. So we included all of them. The table at right describes our inventory categories and how they relate to a number of ZE programs. In all cases, we have relied on self-reported data from our online inventory form to categorize projects.

There are many more “solar homes” than zero-energy homes — where PV systems were added to relatively inefficient homes, and don’t come close to meeting the homes’ annual energy demands.

There are also projects touted as zero net energy that are actually only zero net electricity — that is, other energy sources (e.g., natural gas, propane, or solid fuels) used in the buildings are not accounted for in the energy balance.

	Description: Documentation must show that the renewable energy system...	Qualifying Programs
Net Producer	Supplies 110% or more of the annual energy demand	N/A
ZE	Supplies 100% or more of the annual energy demand	ILFI Zero Energy Building Certification Thousand Home Challenge (THC must designate project as ZE)
ZE-ready	Can supply 90% or more of the annual energy demand (or could, if/when renewable energy is added or system capacity is increased); AND/OR energy use data are not available	DOE ZERH Earth Advantage Net Zero & Net Zero Ready PHI ‘Classic’, ‘Plus’ & ‘Premium’ PHIUS+ Thousand Home Challenge

LEED and virtually all other North American green building programs address energy efficiency and/or renewable energy in some fashion, but just a few explicitly identify or reward zero energy projects. Those that do collaborated with NZEC in developing the project categories used in our inventory and database project.

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INVENTORY HISTORY

Thank you, stalwart inventory contributors!

The Coalition's inventory project was born out of a desire to answer some key questions about the burgeoning zero energy movement:

- Is the movement really making headway? How fast?
- Where are the hotbeds of ZE construction activity?
- Who's leading the charge? Who are the laggards?
- What kind of performance are ZE projects achieving?

Answers to these questions at a meaningful level of detail are only available from those creating the ZE projects. This inventory is therefore the result of extensive, repetitive (and perhaps, occasionally, annoying) outreach to builders, developers, architects, consultants, advocates, local agencies, utilities, non-profits, and others who are directly engaged with ZE projects. We thank you for your time and dedication to this initiative! Without you, we would have nothing to report.

When we first began the inventory in 2015, Coalition stakeholders believed that the information we collected would not only yield answers to the basic questions above, but could also provide insight into the effectiveness of ZE-oriented policies, programs, and incentives – for example, would we observe a correlation between ZE building activity and local initiatives? This in turn might teach us how to encourage greater ZE adoption and thus accelerate our transition to a clean energy future.

The 2015 and 2016 inventories did indeed yield some illuminating facts:

- The 2015 data showed a 50-50 split between single-family and multifamily ZE projects; 2016, however, showed multifamily pulling into the lead by a substantial margin (58%)
- In 2016, 94% of all projects (both single- and multifamily) comprised two or more units; i.e., the majority were not custom projects but instead commercial developments, either for-sale or rental
- Geographic concentrations do in fact occur in areas with strong ZE policies and programs (notably, California and the Northeast)
- Conversely, individuals are also making their mark – there are several areas with relatively high ZE penetration that clearly reflect the efforts of one builder, developer, or consulting organization

Read more of the findings from our first two inventories:

To Zero and Beyond: Zero Energy Residential Buildings Study

(Download 2015 report [HERE](#), 2016 report [HERE](#))

ABOUT THE COALITION

NZEC's mission is to accelerate the market adoption of zero energy and zero carbon buildings and communities across North America. The Coalition exists to amplify the effectiveness of its members and allies through collective action.

Buildings and their energy use account for 41% of carbon emissions in the United States (DOE 2011). The 2016 United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP22) established the goal of keeping the increase in global temperature well below 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels, and pursuing efforts to limit it to 1.5 degrees Celsius. The World Green Building Council (WGBC), in its May 2017 report, *From Thousands to Billions*, states that in order to meet this imperative, all new buildings must operate at net zero carbon by 2030 and 100 percent of all buildings must operate at net zero carbon by 2050.

The next few years will be pivotal for the growing zero energy movement, with new cities and states implementing zero energy and zero carbon policies and programs, solar cell efficiency continuing to climb while prices drop, and demand growing globally for zero energy and zero carbon buildings.

Lux Research projects zero energy buildings and nearly-zero energy buildings will grow to a \$1.3 trillion market by 2025. This illuminates a major market opportunity for the entire construction industry. At the same time, new challenges are emerging for the ZE community: dramatically reducing not only operating energy, but also embodied energy and carbon in building construction; eliminating fossil fuel combustion from building operations; incorporating storage and intelligent load-balancing controls while modernizing and stabilizing the electric grid; reforming planning practices that are counter to our climate goals; and retrofitting our enormous stock of existing buildings.

The Coalition is dedicated to supporting the ZE community in tackling these major tasks through collaborative projects. The inventory was just such a collective action: with NZEC as the catalyzing agent, more than 1,000 individuals and organizations accomplished this project, working together under a shared framework. We look forward to further work with all of you to put more powerful tools and resources in the hands of change agents across the stakeholder spectrum.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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We also thank our members and sponsors (shown below) for their important financial support for this project and for our larger mission.

Our thanks, as well, to each individual who took the time to provide project data or help spread the word about the inventory.

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Project manager & data analysis: Núria Casquero-Modrego

Special acknowledgement: Shilpa Sankaran, former NZEC executive director

COLLABORATING ORGANIZATIONS

Architecture 2030 • Build It Green • Earth Advantage Institute • International Living Future Institute • New Buildings Institute • North American Passive House Network • Northeast Sustainable Energy Association (NESEA) • Passive House California • Passive House Institute of the US (PHIUS) • RESNET • Structural Insulated Panel Association • Thousand Home Challenge • US Department of Energy

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JOIN THE MOVEMENT

NZEC's mission is to accelerate the market adoption of zero energy and zero carbon buildings and communities across North America. The Coalition exists to amplify the effectiveness of its members and allies through collective action. Here's how you can get involved:

Report your project or refer other projects and builders for the next inventory: <http://netzeroenergycoalition.com/zero-energy-inventory/>

Join NZEC for exclusive access to member resources and benefits: <http://netzeroenergycoalition.com/take-action/join-the-coalition/>

Become a sponsor for recognition as a ZE movement leader. Drive the market and create change: <http://netzeroenergycoalition.com/take-action/become-a-sponsor/>

Sign up for the PULSE on Zero Energy newsletter: <http://netzeroenergycoalition.com/discover/newsletter-signup/>

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